

User-Centric Development of a Spiral-Tray Pencil Holder Manufactured from Recycled Bioplastic (PLA)

Aaron Nathanael, SMA Kristen Penabur Kota Wisata

Sub Category: Science and Technology

Introduction

The growing demand for sustainable materials has led to plenty of attention directed to the potential application of recycling within the polymer industry. Currently, Recycled PLA (Polylactic Acid) is widely being turned into fresh 3D-printing filament, eco-friendly packaging like bottles and film, medical products such as tissue scaffolds, as well as textiles and automotive components. serving as an eco-friendly alternative by repurposing waste from food containers, packaging, and failed prints. However, it is not seen to have a significant adoption in the ergonomics and office settings, primarily due to preference over strong metals (steel, aluminum) and sturdy plastics, and the differences of design for each product that inhibit a "one size fits all" scenario.

One such item is the pencil holder, which is a cylindrical cup used to store a wide variety of stationery or writing instruments, such as pens, pencils, scissors, and erasers; whose emergence is closely related to the invention & development of pencils and pencil cases. Early means of storage for writing implements can be traced back to brush pots in ancient China, where bamboo or ceramic cylinders held calligraphy brushes that were essential for writing and drawing during that time period (Cole, 2019). With the discovery of high-quality graphite deposits in the 1500s, craftsmen began assembling graphite with wood, incentivizing people to secure pencils in small boxes to prevent loss or damage (Petroski, 1992). Then, the rise of formal education throughout the late 1800s and early 1900s subsequently increased the demand for industrial-produced pencil cases as students needed to easily carry all their writing tools, whereby in result, several patents were released, dedicated to creating pencil-holding devices. However, the modern open "cup-style" pencil holders did not become widely-known until the 19th and early 20th century, as stationery pivoted to consumer goods or staples when mass-produced pencils, pens, and office supplies created a need for a simple desk organizer. Additionally, it was not until this time when early U.S patents started to show dedicated pen and pencil holders (Lindberg, 1904). By the mid-20th century, the cylindrical cups had become ubiquitous in workplaces and schools due to its low cost, large capacity, and simplicity of manufacture, by which the design has remained largely unchanged, consisting of one open compartment intended to hold a variety of writing tools.

A contemporary pencil holder is typically placed on a desk or table, making it preferred by office workers and students who want to keep said important tools close to them. Its can-like design allows it to contain items in 1 large bulk, solidifying its purpose in a work or school environment. However, a handful of problems occur when large objects clump up and concentrate in a single holder. A group of writing implements like standard markers, 2B pencils, and biros may take so much space such that smaller yet of equal importance tools that rest at the bottom namely compact erasers, the caps of a highlighter or correction tapes, and prism sharpeners often be obturated from a person's reach. The foremost and simplest way to grab hold of them is to ultimately empty the holder off all its content, which could get tedious

and even messy considering all the objects that have to be put out for the sake of getting one of them out. For an industrious person, this action is seen as time-consuming and a hindrance, since they have to be the one who puts them all back in place after unloading the holder, not taking in account of the potential dust and junk that go with the stationery (Rizky, 2023).

A preventive measure can be implemented to reduce cases of all the burden. By having the smaller instruments neatly segregated from the sizeable utensils, this ensures that they do not have to be left obstructed at the bottom in the first place. The pencil holders have seen little to no development since its refinement in the mid 20th century, along with the fact that no patented solution has seen to have been drafted to address this problem. Therefore, the author would like to offer innovative and solution-oriented ideas in the form of an improvised design of a pencil holder.

Content

The proposed holder sees a central cylindrical container housed within a wider outer cylinder of less height, with the central having evenly-spaced rectangular slabs that are spirally jointed to the main holder and the wall of the outer layer, creating segmented compartments that elevate and separate smaller items. The inner cylinder serves as the primary storage space for long writing tools such as pencils or pens. This design allows smaller stationery items, such as erasers, sharpeners, or paper slips to lie visibly on the raised slabs rather than sinking to the very bottom, while the taller central cylinder preserves conventional vertical storage for larger tools. Additionally, with the inner cylinder having of taller height than the outer, it prevents the aforementioned items of smaller size to potentially fall or drop into the main storage. However, they still retain chances of doing the same into the wider cylinder, so an opening is carved out at the bottom near the lowest slab to ensure that access is possible without adjusting the compartment's rotational envelope, rendering the tool redundant for advancing rotation.

The previous chapter suggests that a single compartment approach creates usability an issue that larger writing tools obstruct retrieval of smaller utensils, because the most logical way in order to reach them is by having the entire holder near or fully emptied. Consequently, the dust or debris, originating from a variety of different sources, that comes along with the compartment's insides have a chance of causing a health hazard for those who have respiratory problems related to nerve sensitivity like sinusitis/allergies and asthma (De Grove et al., 2018). Such diseases get triggered through an allergic reaction towards outdoor particulate matter, causing inflammation, airway tightening, mucus production; causing coughing, wheezing, and shortness of breath (Kasjono, 2005). Furthermore, on a psychological aspect, pulling out the pencils and pens could get tedious and even messy considering all the objects that have to be put out for the sake of getting one of them out. For an industrious person, this action is seen as time-consuming and a hindrance, since they have to be the one who puts them all back in place after unloading the holder (Rizky, et al., 2023).

As seen on Attachment 1 and 4, this improvised design of a pencil holder aims to reduce the chances of such events happening by having the smaller objects separated and placed into the mini containments that spirally surround the main pencil holder, granting predetermined placement of small writing tools which make them visible while still maintaining traditional vertical storage for long items. Furthermore, this so-called storage for the compact instruments is sized accordingly and attached in between 2 walls so that they can withstand a number of

weight and quantity in each confinement. A lot of pencil holders tend to not make use of its hollow interior and are kept as an intact cylinder. Attachment 2 and 3 attempt to manifest a different idea, with 2 openings carved across one another. While the same thing can be said about doing of similar method to a ubiquitous pencil holder, it is not just an access hole, but a combination of segregation and entry system that prevents small items from ever becoming buried. Besides that, the openings are only in the walls of the outer cylinder, which is not meant to confine the bigger office instruments in the first place, giving more transparency to the small object that just so happened to fall. Finally, the opening positioned adjacent to the lowest tray is designed to minimize the effort required to access it from the top.

The spiral tray arrangement that is incorporated here is a premeditated functional design choice. Spiral configurations tend to maintain stability and bear capacity better under imperfections or damage because the shape allows them to distribute force along the curve rather than concentrating it on a single angle, as seen in one study, where a spiral reticulated shell is compared to traditional radial-rib shells. Allowing the bending and twisting motion in a spiral structure to act like a natural shock absorber, or what is commonly referred to as energy dissipation (Liu et al., 2021). Moreover, the human hand prefers certain geometries of which they can apply torque or rotation smoothly in a way that complies to its anatomy. Fortunately, human ergonomic studies support that circular/cylindrical or rounded handle-like geometries enhance rotational usability and comfort (Seo & Armstrong, 2022). For reference standard cylindrical handle dimensions on wrench-like tools allowed users to exert greater wrist torque strength compared to non-optimal shapes (Dianat et al., 2017). Thus, having a spiral layout in a cylindrical holder leverages those ergonomic benefits.

The overall design, which includes the trays, carved holes, and the sizing of both the inner and outer cylinders, is intentionally created to be straightforward. Because these elements are purely mechanical and rely on basic structural features, such that the product does not require any computer-controlled component to function. Users can interact with it directly without needing sensors, motors, or programming. Adhering to this simplicity makes the item easier to manufacture, operate, and maintain, while also reducing production costs, as studies in industrial and manufacturing indicate that refraining from using computer-controlled components can reduce overall manufacturing expenses by 20–30% due to fewer materials, shorter assembly times, and minimized quality-control requirements.

Another way to make it more cost efficient and comply to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is to by using recycled PLA (Polylactic Acid). Doing so resuscitates the thermoplastic and addresses the overall plastic burden by up to 50% if properly incorporated with reusing, recycling, and composting systems, primarily due to its reusability and since it requires less carbon footprint during production; supporting a circular economy (Khan & Jan, 2025). On top of that, under optimized extrusion conditions like a narrow temperature window of 180-205 degrees Celcius, recycled PLA grants ease of production especially through 3D printing by offering tensile strength or interlayer adhesion comparable to that of virgin PLA (Naveed et al., 2025). Whereas, frequently used materials like virgin petroleum-based plastics and metal respectively generate more high volumes of air emissions by almost three-fold (80%) when high incineration rates are taken into consideration (European Commission, 2004) and have an economic value basis of 1100 kg CO₂-eq per US\$1000 (Strezov et al., 2021).

Closing

The proposed spiral-tray pencil holder demonstrates how a simple everyday object can be improved through thoughtful engineering, ergonomic considerations, and sustainable material choices. By elevating smaller stationery items onto spiraled trays, the design solves the long-standing issue of compact tools becoming buried beneath larger ones, a problem that creates clutter, slows productivity, and can even expose users to accumulated dust. The incorporation of a taller central cylinder, strategic openings, and structurally efficient spiral geometry helps ensure visibility, accessibility, and user comfort, while keeping the overall mechanism purely mechanical and easy to manufacture. Through this approach, the design maintains its ergonomic nature and offers a practical solution that aligns with the main problem identified in the early sections of the paper.

In addition to improving usability, this innovation demonstrates the potential of recycled PLA as a meaningful alternative to conventional materials in office and ergonomic products. Using recycled PLA supports a circular economy, reduces environmental impact, and remains compatible with cost-effective manufacturing methods such as 3D printing. As an aspiring mechanical engineer, the author hopes that this work encourages greater adoption of eco-friendly materials in everyday items and inspires future improvements in user-centered product design. Ultimately, the spiral-tray pencil holder serves as an example of how sustainability, ergonomics, and mechanical simplicity can coexist to create a more efficient and accessible tool for everyday users.

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Attachment (12 pt)

Attachment 1. Bird's-eye overview of the design.

Attachment 2. Carving of the outer cylinder closest adjacent to the bottom-most tray.

Attachment 3. The carving across the bottom-most tray.

Attachment 4. Top view of the holder.

